

WOMEN ENTREPRENEURS OF UZBEKISTAN ARE MEMBERS OF THE INTERNATIONAL GLOBAL INDEX OF WOMEN'S ENTREPRENEURSHIP

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Abstract: The article describes the history of entrepreneurship, the activities of the "Business Woman" association of businesswomen of Uzbekistan, and the admission to the membership of the "International Global Index of Women's Entrepreneurship".

Keywords: economy, women, market relations, international project, "Businesswoman" association, international global index.

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The market was created as a result of the creation of material goods in society, production as an important industry that serves to satisfy people's vital needs, and its branches. If you look at the long history of the market economy, you can witness that it is a progressive force that ensures the economic development of the society and increases the well-being of people. In fact, the three major divisions of labor in the history of human society, the separation of animal husbandry from hunting, and the emergence of agriculture and handicrafts were the beginnings of human creation of material goods and entrepreneurship based on the opportunities provided by nature.

The word businessman (entrepreneurship). the first times in the English economy in the 18th century appear is property the owner said the meaning means occupies an important place in the economy due to its specific aspects, such as low capital expenditure requirements, quick adaptation to the changing requirements of the market economy, filling the domestic market with high-quality and competitive food products, and increasing the export potential.

Regarding the support of small business and entrepreneurship in the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On the protection of private property and guarantees of the rights of owners", "On the procedures for granting permission in the field of entrepreneurial activity", "On family entrepreneurship", "On the guarantees of the freedom of entrepreneurial activity" " (in the new version), "On measures to further strengthen the guarantees of women's labor rights and support entrepreneurship" ¹⁹⁷and more than fifteen other normative documents, as a result of the adoption of

¹⁹⁷ <https://www.lex.uz> .

the labor-capable layer of the population, including women favorable conditions for entrepreneurship and business are being created, and their place in the economy is being strengthened.

It should be noted that women are not only the main source of the nation's gene pool, but also a great labor resource in the country's economy. "Tadbirkor Ayl" Association of Business Women of Uzbekistan has a special place in the practical work carried out to increase the socio-economic activity of women, to attract and develop them to entrepreneurship, and to expand their rights and opportunities.

The activities of the "Businesswoman" association are aimed at creating favorable conditions for the active participation of women in market relations, supporting their entrepreneurial initiatives, and protecting their rights and interests in business.

businesswomen of Uzbekistan " **Businesswoman** " was founded on June 21, 1991. Goals and objectives of the association:

- women to adapt to the emerging new cocktail market, to support their business initiatives, to protect the rights of women entrepreneurs,

- It is to promote the interests of the members of the association, to support various forms of entrepreneurship, to strengthen the atmosphere of mutual trust in practical cooperation ¹⁹⁸.

Businesswomen of Uzbekistan " **Businesswoman** " association has its divisions in 14 regions of the republic. The number of women entrepreneurs today is more than 165,000. Women make up 34 percent of the total number of heads of small businesses and entrepreneurship entities. 7% of farms (5066) are headed by women ¹⁹⁹.

In our country, a unique model of financial support by the state has been created to attract women to entrepreneurship and support them. The volume of loans allocated by commercial banks for the comprehensive development of women's entrepreneurship is increasing year by year. Over the past years, more than 200,000 new jobs have been created on the basis of the projects implemented by the members of the "Businesswoman" association. According to the social order of the Public Fund under the Oliy Majlis, "Widely involving graduates of secondary special and higher educational institutions, women and disabled people living in 10 districts of economic and social development below the republican level, in family business and various fields of private entrepreneurship, ensuring their employment, as well as modern "helping them master information technologies" project was implemented, 128 unemployed women in each district were trained for

¹⁹⁸ Ya.P. Asminkin and others. Women's NGOs of Uzbekistan. Reference
.- Tashkent, Publishing House, 2000, - P.38-39

¹⁹⁹ www.standart.uz/The number of women entrepreneurs in Uzbekistan

re-employment and were trained in the basics of business. A total of 1,024 unemployed women were included in this process, and about 1,000 were provided with jobs.

The association is implementing a number of projects at the international level. In particular, in cooperation with the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe, on the basis of the project "Improvement of women's business education and development of young women's entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan", a special training program was held for young businesswomen in the field of business basics. On the basis of the program, the participants were in the Netherlands and shared their experiences with their colleagues.

In cooperation with the Islamic Development Bank, 15 women were able to receive small grants from the Islamic Development Bank within the framework of the "Project to support women's employment, socially oriented innovative business projects".

With the support of the World Bank, the project "Development of the fruit and vegetable sector in Uzbekistan" provides close support to women working in farmers, peasants and horticultural households ²⁰⁰.

Every year, the traditional "ANOR" competition held by the Business Women's Association of Uzbekistan in cooperation with the Banks Association of Uzbekistan serves to ensure the implementation of the above priority tasks.

In 2020, the implementation of the innovative project "Creation of a system of conducting women's entrepreneurship in Uzbekistan based on the requirements of the international global index" by the Association of Business Women of Uzbekistan with the support of the Ministry of Innovative Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2020 will be the business ecosystem in our country and the prospects of the potential of business women in it, among about 100 countries of the world. made it possible to determine the rating ²⁰¹.

"Women's Entrepreneurship Global Index" measures the development prospects of women's entrepreneurship around the world. The quality of development of women's entrepreneurship is determined by 3 main factors: entrepreneurial environment, entrepreneurial ecosystem and women's desire to engage in entrepreneurship.

It can be said that the participation of Uzbekistan in this global rating serves to perform a comparative analysis of the state of women's entrepreneurship among developed countries, to identify existing problems through global rating indicators, to determine measures to further improve the environment of women's

²⁰⁰ . [https // Own.A](https://Own.A). Women entrepreneurs contribute to the development of the country. 20.11.2019.

²⁰¹ [https // ngo.uz](https://ngo.uz). Participation of Uzbekistan in the global index of women's entrepreneurship.

entrepreneurship, and also to achieve a positive approach of the international community.

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